

Physio- chemical characterization of different types of Gall stones

Shristi Kumari, Rajani Sharma

Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Amity university Jharkhand, Ranchi, India

Email: kumari.shristi2862@gmail.com

Gallstones are hardened deposits of digestive fluid like bile, bilirubin, cholesterol, calcium salts, amino acids and other materials which are formed within the gallbladder. With the change in lifestyle, ageing and food habits gallstones are a major affliction seen around the world. Based on physiological and chemical structure gallstones can be classified as cholesterol, pigmented, and mixed gallstones. The difference in the composition of gallstone is also influenced by the epidemiological factor. In western countries there is predominance of cholesterol gallstone whereas in India there is no such specification. In southern India there is predominance of pigmented gallstone, but cholesterol gallstone is more prone in northern region of India. This differences in their composition also effects the treatment methodology. Till date mostly medicine has been seen effective against cholesterol gallstone only. But there is various evidence where there is predominance of pigmented gallstone. With this respect we aim to find the prevalence of types of gallstones in Jharkhand region. This will be helpful to adopt the treatment methodology or designing target specific drug.

Key Words: Gallstone, Cholecystectomy, chemical composition.